

Towards a roadmap for collaboration in DARIAH: The JRC approach

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Abstract

DARIAH-EU (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) is a pan-European consortium supporting digitally enabled research across the arts and humanities, with its Working Groups (WGs) functioning as a core mechanism for community-driven activities. This paper presents a methodological approach to mapping synergies and collaboration potential among DARIAH WGs, with the aim of identifying connections that can strengthen cross-WG cooperation and inform future infrastructure strategy. The study addresses how WGs relate in terms of scope, resources, and community; what challenges they face; how a culture of collaboration can be cultivated; and how WGs can both leverage and contribute to DARIAH central services. A three-step methodology is applied, comprising the selection of WG initiatives, the identification of connections through metadata-based analysis, and the showcasing of successful collaborative use cases. Disciplines reported in the 2025 WG activity reports were normalised against the ÖFOS 2012 vocabulary and activities against the TaDiRaH taxonomy, with results rendered through interactive chord and Sankey diagrams. Analysis of 17 active WGs spanning 17 scientific areas and 7 activity types reveals Other Humanities, Computer Sciences, and the Arts as the most frequently represented disciplinary areas, while Annotating, Organizing, Disseminating, and Archiving emerge as the most widely shared digital research activities. Collaborative initiatives such as the ECHOLOT project demonstrate the strategic value of joint proposals. The paper concludes by proposing future directions for impact measurement, knowledge base integration, and funding mechanisms that prioritise cross-WG collaboration as a driver for sustainable, infrastructure-wide innovation in the European digital humanities landscape.

Keywords: Digital Humanities, Open Science, Data infrastructures, RI communities

1. Introduction

DARIAH-EU (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) is a pan-European consortium supporting digitally enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. It was established in 2014 as an European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), aiming at connecting researchers, tools, and data, as well as providing infrastructure to promote knowledge exchange, digital methods and open science practices¹.

DARIAH-EU is constituted by its Executive Bodies (General Assembly and Board of Directors), Advisory Bodies (Scientific Board), Coordinating Bodies (National Coordinators Committee, Senior Management Team), Implementation Bodies (Joint Research Committee and Working Groups) and Administrative Bodies (DARIAH Coordination Office).

In particular, the Joint Research Committee² (JRC) consists of a group of experts in charge of advising the Board of Directors, producing annual activity reports, and evaluating in-kind contributions as well as guiding the development of digital tools, services, and data for arts

¹ <https://www.dariah.eu/about/mission-vision/>

² <https://www.dariah.eu/about/organisation-and-governance/#joint-research-committee>

and humanities research. Key activity of the Committee is the communication with the Working Groups (WG),³ which are joint community activities in DARIAH contributing to strategic areas, fostering knowledge transfer across groups and facilitating their research. The overarching objective of JRC's oversight of the communities' activities is to trailblaze cutting-edge directions in Digital Humanities and the Arts by enabling and supporting novel approaches and exploration of small scale, modestly budgeted activities. There are currently more than twenty active WGs, having synergies between them as well as common goals, needs and challenges.

This study intends to identify the connections and synergies between WGs in order to better understand the current landscape across DARIAH communities, as well as future directions. In particular, this paper intends to answer the following questions (but not limited to):

- Can we draw parallels and links between WGs and are there any commonalities in scope, resources, operation or community?
- What are the challenges that WGs currently face and how they can benefit from communicating and transferring knowledge and experiences from other WGs?
- How can WG grow as a culture of collaboration that would facilitate creating impact through shared activities?
- How can WGs leverage central services of DARIAH-EU?
- How can WGs contribute to the development of DARIAH central services?
- Can WGs be (partially) responsible for sustainability and maintenance of existing or new DARIAH central services?

The paper is organised as follows: after a brief introduction, previous work within DARIAH and Digital Humanities (DH) is introduced. Then, an analysis of the current situation concerning WGs in DARIAH is presented, in combination with data research infrastructures and successful projects. Finally, this work concludes with final remarks and future work.

2. Related work

The data and research infrastructure landscape in Digital Humanities in Europe is rapidly evolving to new and innovative ecosystems. Advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) are providing a new context in which data is playing a key role. Data for training AI models is key in all these initiatives and this necessitates routines about data quality diagnostics, data transformation, fusion, integration and twining. Open Science is an essential element in this new context aiming at democratising access to data. Cultural Heritage has been for decades a sector in which data has been produced according to international standards [1]. Recent initiatives such as FAIR and Collections as Data adopted by relevant actors such as European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and Europeana, are focused on the provision of research data, including digital collections to support computational access [2, 3, 4]. Other approaches are focused instead on the responsible reuse of the data considering the benefit of the society and the adoption of ethical patterns [5]. Common European data spaces, research infrastructures and other European initiatives, such as the Cultural Heritage Cloud (or the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage), are changing traditional means to access data and digital collections.

³ <https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups-list/>

The DARIAH Strategic Plan [7] focuses on four main pillars: i) the provision of a marketplace to share data, tools and services; ii) giving access to education and training; iii) the creation of thematic WGs; and iv) building bridges between research policy and communities of practice. These pillars aim to strengthen the voice of arts and humanities in Europe focusing on Open Science in a digital environment. Recent Strategy priorities include a renewed “[a]im for Communities pillar: strengthen distributed and interdisciplinary research network, increase support and visibility for WGs and regional hubs, launch DARIAH spotlight and signature project, broaden participation”.

In line with the strategic plan, DARIAH has released several scholarly communities’ platforms for different purposes. The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace⁴ is a platform in which communities are able to share data, tools and services, using a collaborative system. In terms of education and teaching, DARIAH campus⁵ enables the publication of training materials in the form of courses and curricula. During the last years, DARIAH has established a list of WGs focusing on different topics according to the needs and requirements of the community. For instance, the Bibliographical data (Bibliodata) WG [8] fosters the cooperation between all the parties involved in the bibliographical data life and the DHwiki group is focused on the dissemination of use case experiences and best practices around Wikibase and Wikidata in a DH context [9]. ARCHETIPO WG [10] promotes collaboration across the communities who are working with built heritage and its history through knowledge representations and semantic annotation. In total, there are more than twenty active WGs, addressing a wide diversity of topics.

DARIAH WGs connect actors from different backgrounds and disciplines such as researchers, practitioners, policymakers or citizens. WGs members have regular meetings to share ideas and knowledge and are in charge of different tasks such as webinars, events and publication of reports, workshops, training activities, research articles and white papers. Previous work investigated collaborative practices taking place in the DARIAH WGs, identifying the concept of co-creation as a key element in knowledge creation, by focussing on the epistemic and socio/political dynamics created by the interaction of practices and governance models proper of Research Infrastructures and Research Communities [6]. Other initiatives from other domains such as Wikimedia or AI4LAM⁶ also created WGs concerning different topics focusing on community building, or AI techniques such as the use of LLM for the automation of metadata creation or the use of computer vision techniques for OCR.

Despite all this work, none of the previous approaches is focused on the analysis of the work, relationships and goals of WGs in the context of resource management and reuse at DARIAH level. This work is interesting not only to help define future directions for DARIAH strategy, but also for DH researchers and practitioners, in order to identify potential needs, connections and challenges in existing and new WGs.

⁴ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

⁵ <https://campus.dariah.eu/>

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/ai4lam>

3. Methodology

This section describes the methodology employed to identify the commonalities, map collaboration potential and understand possible benefits of WGs working in a coordinated way. The methodology involves three steps: selection of a WG initiative or project, identification of connections between WGs, and showcasing success stories and impactful use cases. These are relevant to demonstrate the impact and outputs of the work performed in the context of DARIAH communities.

The selection of the initiative can be performed according to different features including for instance the topic addressed (e.g., DH or Open Science), the size of the initiative and number of WGs engaged or the geographic extension (local, regional, national or international) of the network established. Depending on the needs, the criteria can be adapted to the requirements.

In order to identify possible connections and information exchange or contacts between WGs, the metadata describing each of the WGs can be employed to find connections. The metadata provides information describing the disciplines involved in each WG. Based on this information, visualisations can be created in order to show and illustrate how the WGs are connected in terms of operating within specific disciplines.

Traditional means to show relationships between entities visualising connections and hierarchies include dendrograms and diagrams such as Sankey [12]. For example, *chord diagrams* show the structure of paired connections between the instances of the same level in which every instance is represented by an arc. Every connection is shown as a band with (potential) various start and end widths to depict differences in input and output. This type of charts can reveal complex relationships that might be hard to find when using a lot of data. A *Sankey diagram* is a type of visualization to display flows from one set of values to another. It shows entities that represent the values and connects them by links, or flows. Each flow has a varying height, which depends on its quantity. Colors can be employed to distinguish flows.

The last step of the process involves showcasing successful stories and use cases aiming at demonstrating good practices and encouraging cross-WG collaboration. Those narratives can be identified in blogs, research sections, white papers, workshop results and research publications. In general, institutions publish outputs in different platforms, some of them can be hosted by them and others not such as Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

4. Results

This section describes the results obtained after implementing the methodology described in Section 3 to the analysis of the existing DARIAH WGs characteristics in terms of disciplinary scope and types of scholarly activities. Compared to other infrastructures, DARIAH engages a large number of WGs thus enabling a more detailed and extended analysis of their operation and activities. The results of this enquiry are presented in the following subsections.

4.1. Identifying the connection between WGs in DARIAH

A preliminary analysis was performed to identify the disciplines and digital research activities covered by the WGs, based on the information they provided in their 2025 activity reports. Disciplines were normalised against the [ÖFOS 2012 vocabulary](#) and activities against the [TaDiRaH taxonomy](#), both used in the SSH Open Marketplace. The analysis covers 17 active WGs, spanning 17 broad scientific areas and 7 broad activity types. The results are illustrated through two interactive charts accessible online. Figure 1 shows the disciplines covered by the WGs in a hierarchical view and Figure 2 maps each WG to the activities reported.

Figure 1. Disciplines covered by DARIAH WGs grouped by broader scientific areas. Based on the disciplines reported in the 2025 WG reports. The interactive chart available at <https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/28838029/>

The broader scientific areas most frequently associated with the WGs are Other Humanities (13 WGs), Computer Sciences (9), Arts (8), Media and Communication Sciences (8), Philosophy and Ethics (6), History and Archaeology (5), Linguistics and Literature (5), and Sociology (4).

Figure 2. Digital research activities of DARIAH WGs mapped to the TaDiRaH taxonomy, based on the 2025 WG activity reports. Flows link each WG to the activities mentioned. The interactive chart available at <https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/28841266/>

The Sankey diagram shows, on the left, each WG and the number of distinct digital research activities it lists and, on the right, each activity and the number of WGs that mention it. The flows do not represent joint work, but thematic overlap. Multilingual DH (19 activities), Sustainable publishing of (meta)data (14) and AI and Music (11) report the broadest range of activities. The most widely shared activities are Annotating, Organizing, Disseminating, and Archiving (each in 5 WGs), followed by Analyzing, Collaborating, Modeling, Preserving and Teaching (each in 4 WGs).

This analysis by means of a dynamic visualisation provides relevant information concerning the WGs. Potential insights to be provided by this include: i) a researcher is willing to identify what are the WGs related to Media and Communication Sciences; ii) align funding opportunities according to a particular topic such as Computer Science with existing WGs; and iii) identify needs and disciplines not covered for the potential creation of new WGs. Or

in terms of internal functions, a group of scholars, members of a WG, want to organise a place-based activity such as a data collection and co-creation workshop and want to liaise with other WGs who may have already used specific relevant tools and resources in similar enquiries.

4.2. Use cases and best practices

This section presents successful initiatives in terms of funding and activities based on the collaboration of several WGs in DARIAH. Some examples of impact stories are based on project proposals obtaining funding as part of the work of several DARIAH WGs in combination with other institutions. For example, the Bibliodata and DhWiki WGs worked together in the EU-funded project ECHOLOT (European Cultural Heritage Optimised Linked Open Tools), that supports the development and adoption of the Cultural Heritage Cloud's (ECCCH) digital infrastructure by researchers and institutions across Europe [14]. ECHOLOT facilitates the simultaneous publication of high-quality, semantically rich and interoperable data by aggregators such as Europeana and the common European data space for cultural heritage, as well as citizen science platforms from the Wikimedia ecosystem. Other WGs, such as UDigiSH, contribute to ARCHETIPO research implementation, by means of tools of heritage knowledge representation for safeguarding threatened cultural heritage which were previously developed in the context of nationally funded research [15]. New funding opportunities within DARIAH and WGs encourages the collaboration of WGs by supporting joint proposals.⁷ Another example is cross-WGs collaboration enabled through DARIAH funding as in the case of joint workshops⁸ that led to the creation of new workflows and publications. These are strategic in terms of testing and prototyping activities that can be scaled up.

Another aspect to highlight is the impact of the outputs. Several frameworks are available to measure impact such as D-Craft [13]. These frameworks enable the measurement of the impact in society and research in order to provide a standardised way to measure impact and reuse. In the particular case of WGs within DARIAH EU, platforms such as DARIAH Campus and the SSH Open Marketplace are employed to make outputs available. Some examples include training courses, datasets, publications or workflows. Overall, so far, a total number of 18 resources created through WG activities are available in the SSH Open Marketplace. Other key contributions by WGs to the DARIAH community include list of dedicated reference libraries on the DARIAH Zotero library⁹ and training material on Dariah Campus by the WGs dariahTeach, GeoHumanities, ELDAH, ARCHETIPO, Teatralia and UDigiSH.

⁷ <https://www.dariah.eu/2025/09/19/dariah-working-groups-funding-call-2026-2027-call-for-projects/>

⁸

https://www.google.com/url?q=https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/2024&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1779395601215889&usg=AOvVaw1zYcyyb_tbuFMvF-I9bfz3

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https://www.google.com/url?q=https://www.zotero.org/groups/744474/dariah/collections/QCNEL2K7/collection&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1779395601211104&usg=AOvVaw3S4C964Bpe4soyygRuG_-O

4.3. Discussion

The results obtained in this work are limited in scope. For instance, this study is focused on DARIAH EU as the main scholarly community environment. In terms of visualisation, two examples are provided as a preliminary effort of visually analysing dynamically evolving communities of research practice. Arguably, these visualisations can be extended with additional examples employing additional metadata fields and providing other types of visualisations not covered in this work. Note that this work can be extended and applied to other domains by adjusting each of the steps to other topics and initiatives.

It is important to notice that while a successful story is documented in this work concerning a project proposal, in other cases, project proposals created from several WGs were not funded. However, the knowledge acquired when coordinating and preparing a proposal as well as the feedback received from the funding agency can be a valuable input for future proposals.

One of the aims of this study is to demonstrate the need for new funding opportunities that can be defined in the context of fostering correlations across several WGs with the objective of re-use of DARIAH resources. This can strengthen the infrastructure communities by creating methodological, epistemological and information bridges between WGs.

5. Conclusions and future work

DARIAH is a community effort aligned with open science principles about sharing knowledge and expertise. The infrastructure's WGs serve as a basis to foster community engagement by means of different activities and collaborative tasks. During the last years, WGs have become an essential, core component of DARIAH. This paper presented existing WGs, their alignments and particularities as well as successful use cases and stories built through the collaboration of several WGs. This study intends to identify best practices, needs and successful examples in order to promote and give more visibility to WGs, and mostly to promote the value of cross-WG collaborations. The relation between WGs showed the potential benefits in terms of knowledge exchange and funding opportunities. Eventually this study envisions to identify WG collaboration obstacles and enabling strategies towards sharing WG resources, common activities and joint objectives, and to provide necessary data for reflecting on how to prioritise initiatives that would contribute new ways to leverage on existing WG results and ongoing research.

Future work to be explored includes the inclusion and extension of the information concerning WGs in the new knowledge base of DARIAH. This development will help promote outputs and results from WGs online and on different platforms. Additional work includes the exploration of TaDiRAH [11] as a taxonomy to describe the activities performed in WGs to refine and improve the connection in WGs as well as the use of existing frameworks to measure impact [13].

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